

RoguePlots_CML-1-Morph: This pdf contains the RoguePlots created for the 24 fossils resulted from the constrained maximum likelihood analysis for each one of the fossils using only morphological data (*CML-1-Morph*).

Figure	page
S1c.Rogue_plotX_Archaenthus_linnenbergeri	2
S2c.Rogue_plotX_Archaestella_verticillatus	3
S3c.Rogue_plotX_Bertilanthus_scanicus	4
S4c.Rogue_plotX_Canrightia_resinifera	5
S5c.Rogue_plotX_Carpestella_lacunata	6
S6c.Rogue_plotX_Cecilanthus_polymerus	7
S7c.Rogue_plotX_Chloranthistemon_endressii	8
S8c.Rogue_plotX_Dakotanthus_cordiformis	9
S9c.Rogue_plotX_Divisestylus_brevistamineus	10
S10c.Rogue_plotX_Florissantia_quilchenensis	11
S11c.Rogue_plotX_Kajanthus_lusitanicus	12
S12c.Rogue_plotX_Mabelia_connatifila	13
S13c.Rogue_plotX_Mauldinia_mirabilis	14
S14c.Rogue_plotX_Microvictoria_svitkoana	15
S15c.Rogue_plotX_Paleocclusia_chevalieri	16
S16c.Rogue_plotX_Paradinandra_suecica	17
S17c.Rogue_plotX_Pentapetalum_trifasciculandricus	18
S18c.Rogue_plotX_Platydiscus_peltatus	19
S19c.Rogue_plotX_Quadriplatanus_georgianus	20
S20c.Rogue_plotX_Rariglanda_jerseyensis	21
S21c.Rogue_plotX_Saururus_tuckerae	22
S22c.Rogue_plotX_Spanomera_mauldinensis	23
S23c.Rogue_plotX_Tylerianthus_crossmanensis	24
S24c.Rogue_plotX_Virginianthus_calycanthoides	25

X_Archaeanthus_linnenbergeri

BS

X *Canrigitia resinifera*

BS

X_Dakotanthus_cordiformis

BS

X_Divisestylus_brevistamineus

X *Florissantia quichenensis*

X. *Mauldinia mirabilis*

X_Pentapetalum_trifasciculandricus

X_Quadriplatanus_georgianus

X. *Saururus tuckerae*

BS

X_Tylerianthus_crossmanensis

